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THE GAME SIMULATION AS A METHOD OF TRAINING FOR TEACHERS OF A HIGHER SCHOOL**ИГРОВОЕ МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ КАК СРЕДСТВО ПОДГОТОВКИ ПРЕПОДАВАТЕЛЕЙ ВЫСШЕЙ ШКОЛЫ**

©Фоминых М.В.

канд. пед. наук,

Российский государственный

профессионально–педагогический университет,

г. Екатеринбург, Россия, fominykh.maria12@yandex.ru

©Fominykh M.

Ph.D., Russian State Vocational Pedagogic University,

Ekaterinburg, Russia, fominykh.maria12@yandex.ru

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается вопрос совершенствования процесса развития педагогических способностей будущих педагогов профессионального образования средствами игрового моделирования, приводятся основные правила игрового моделирования.

Abstract. The question of the perfection of process of development of pedagogical abilities of future teachers of vocational training by means of game simulation is discussed in this article, also the basic rules of the game simulation are provided.

Ключевые слова: игровое моделирование, преподаватель высшей школы, педагог профессионального образования, педагогические способности

Keywords: game simulation, high school teacher, teacher of professional education, teaching abilities

The game simulation may be treated as a research of some pedagogical phenomenon, processes or different pedagogical systems by construction and research of its models with the purpose of their further use in teaching; it's a kind of the game method, an important part in development of a student's pedagogical qualities while the studying process. It is realized through «the immersion» into the concrete situation, modeled in training and educational purposes. It is also assumes the most active position of students. There are three principles of the game simulation.

The first of them is the reflection and transformation principle. The attitude is the game and the objective reality.

The second is the self-expression principle. The attitude is the game and the subject of the game. During the game its subject — the player or an actor expresses his own subjective personal world — subjective reality as of the player as of an imaged character.

The third is the development and game activity principle. The attitude is the game and the previous experience of the game activity.

Study of modern pedagogical literature on the theme of the game simulation allows us to formulate the following conditions of the game simulating:

–free and voluntary inclusion into the game, not to impose the game on, but to draw in it.

–the students should understand the meaning and the maintenance of the game, its rules and the idea of each part.

–the meaning of the game should coincide with the meaning and maintenance of behavior in real situations in order to the main meaning of the play acts could transferee into a real life.

–the participants of the game should be guided by the norms of morality accepted in society, based on humanism and values common to humanity.

–the game should not humiliate its participants.

–The game should have a positive impact on the development of emotional and strong-willed, intellectual, rational and physical sphere.

–the game should be organized, directed and restrained if it is necessary but not suppressed. Each participant should be ensured to have an opportunity to take the initiative.

–it is necessary to impel the students to analyze the game, to compare the imitation with the corresponding part of the real life.

–as a result, the discussion of the game may include the preview of its maintenance, rules etc.

For example, the American scientist Littlewood W. defines the following main rules of the game simulation:

–it is necessary to get used to a definite role in such a situation. In some cases, he can play himself, but in other cases, he will have to take on the role of an imaginary.

– It is necessary to behave like everything happening is a reality.

The game simulation, based on important methodological rules(the partnership style of a game interaction and spatial temporal limitations in the scope of communication between the participants of the game training) has great opportunities, because the game as a model of an objective reality makes its structure more intelligible and finds important causal connections out.

As a result, the game simulation also may be used for the development of a personality's various abilities. Thus, to cope with his work, a teacher should have outstanding teaching abilities. In its turn, development of such teaching abilities is an integral part of a higher schoolteacher's training.

Under the pedagogical abilities, we understand a personality's definite psychological peculiarities, which are a condition of his succeeding in training and education in the role of a teacher.

As for analysis of pedagogical abilities. As far as R.S. Nемов considers, to succeed in a work, a teacher should have outstanding general and special abilities. The general abilities include those, which define high results in any human activity. And the special abilities include those, on which the success of a pedagogical activity, training and education depend. The general abilities are not so important for us, because they are connected not only with a pedagogical activity. But the special abilities we will consider in details. They may include:

–an ability to see and feel, is a student understanding the learning material.

–an ability to select a school material independently.

–an ability to state in different ways, to explain the same material in affordable way to ensure its understanding for each student.

–an ability to take into account an individuality of each student during the teaching ensuring the quick and profound studying, getting skills and abilities.

–an ability to get a significant amount of information, an intellectual and moral development of all students in a short time.

–an ability of a teacher to organize a lesson correctly, perfecting his teaching skills from lesson to lesson.

–an ability to pass an experience to another teachers and to learn from their examples at the same time.

–an ability of self-studying, including the search and creative treatment of an information and its use in a teaching process.

–an ability to form the necessary motivation and structure of teaching for the students.

All these special abilities are connected with three related points of activity for getting knowledge, skills: they are teaching, instruction and learning. We cannot say definitely about how and when they start to form during the ontogenesis and by what principles they are formed. Something in them is inherent and it exists in form of instincts. Still the science is able to tell nothing concrete about it. As all the other abilities, the teaching abilities are trained. In addition, it is possible to form them in adults.

According to the use of the game simulation, the development of teaching abilities happens owing to:

- The development of skills to express ideas and suggestions.
- An improving the skills of interaction with different people.
- Visualization of all the collected ideas.
- The development of pedagogical skills of tact.
- The opportunity to develop your mind, because it is necessary to build an intrigue and realize it.
- The development of psychological plasticity
- The development of skills to navigate in real-life situations by playing them repeatedly, as if, make-believe in his dream world.
- The development of an active attitude to life and sense of purpose in carrying out this goal.

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Written from the screen.

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